

The Judicial and Legislative System in the Society of Prof. Momchil Dobrev's and by Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev's Theory of Socio-Humanism - Against the Judiciary of the Global Mafia Masonic Elite and its Deep Rule

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ABSTRACT: Lord Prof. PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev developed 2006 Theory of socio-humanism by developing the creation of a new human society with a new political, economic, social, health, educational, environmental system, a new system of control of political and other decisions - direct democracy, creating a system of direct democracy in the judiciary, in the legislative system, Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova created in 2006. "Theory of degree of justice / injustice /" as well as "Theory of the degree of democracy" based on their practice in court, prosecution, state and especially the practice of Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev as a judge with decades of experience as such as a civil and a criminal judge. Prof. Momchil Dobrev co-founded 2003 Theory of Corruption and Theory of the Mafia and Theory and Practice of Mafia, which contribute to clearing the Theory of the Degree of Justice / Injustice.

KEY WORDS: Justice, mafia, corruption, theory,.

1.INTRODUCTION

Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Lady Prof. Mariola Garibova developed in 2006. Theory of socio-humanism, which theory represents a social system of political, social, economic, humanistic management of society that opposes the modern capitalism of the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule and deep state.

Theory of socio-humanism, puts the government on a new principled basis, both the political governance of a country in the modern world and the new economic governance in a country based on the new principled basis, the new governance in the judiciary, the new governance in the ecological system, the social system, the system of education, healthcare, climate and ecology, culture and a system of direct control of the whole system - through a system of direct democracy.

The theory of socio-humanism is a critique of modern global neoliberal capitalism and its structure of government both in each country and at the international level and provides a solution for creating a new social system - more harmonious and humanistic and centered on man's ecological system. in which he lives.

The theory of socio-humanism puts new principles in the whole government of a country in accordance with the ecological system, and the creative, creative qualities of each person.

Lord Prof. PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev developed 2006 "Theory of degree of justice / injustice /" based on their practice in court, prosecutor's office, state and especially the practice of Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev as a judge with decades of experience as a civil and criminal judge . Prof. Momchil Dobrev co-founded 2003 Theory of Corruption and Theory of Mafia and Theory and Practice of Mafia, which contribute to clearing the Theory of the Degree of Justice / Injustice.

In the year 2001 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the Theory of the mafia and Theory of corruption. All the both theories has been developed by analyzing the mafia and the corruption all over the world. In Bulgaria, Germany, European Union, and other countries.

In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the 'Theory of Mafiotismus' as a new type of government oriented solely in the private interests of individuals and private institutions.

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In this article we define the system of the institute of the judiciary and the system of lawmaking of a society based on the THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev in the government of a country governed by its principles.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The problem of the crisis of the current capitalist globalist neoliberal society is enormous and leads to the real demise of our civilization.

Theory of socio-humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova create a system for a new society with new principles of social, political, economic, social, ecological life of the countries on the planet Earth. This system of a new society will provide a real rest of civilization and the preservation of this civilization. This system completely replaces the capitalist system which is the real cause of the crises of society, the creation of inequalities, the robbery of entire countries, peoples, consumers of a global Masonic mafia elite that governs countries all over the world through a deep government and deep state.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods of analysis, verification, critique of the leading society and a capitalist global neoliberal system that works only for the benefit of the global Masonic mafia elite.

- Analysis of democracies in the world
- Analysis of political systems
- Analysis of the economic system in the world
- Analysis of the laws of a country.
- Analysis of all authorities in a country - judicial, legislative, executive
- Analysis of the implementation of the laws of a country
- Analysis of managed public resources
- Analysis of the existence of corruption and mafia in the judiciary, in the state system.
- Analysis of the work of the prosecutor's office as a guarantor of the existence and development of mafia.
- Analysis of the judiciary - laws, judges, selection of judges, development of judges, violations of judges, disciplinary and other liability of judges, prosecutors, investigators

3. MORALITY AND JUDGES in the modern neoliberal capitalist society created by the global Masonic mafia-driven elite

The law is accepted as an instrument for control and management of society, of public relations. So the decision and the right cannot be left only in the hands of the judge, provided that he is given unlimited opportunities - to break the law, to legalize theft, of companies, factories, tools, equipment, to terminate cases. who are from the mafia and who have broken the law to the detriment of the victim.

Morality is the distinction between intentions, decisions, and actions against those that are good and right and those that are wrong and bad. Morality is an essential part of the standards and principles that are derived from the guild's code of ethics.

Morality is synonymous with honesty, honesty, diligence, kindness, and righteousness.

However, the moral norms and principles of the judge are uniform, although there are different moral systems.

For the judge and the prosecutor, they are unique and irrevocable.

Immorality is the other side of morality.

After the law, morality is the second source of law in countries that have adopted the continental legal system. If such a morality with the respective qualities is missing, then there is no right and the law is not realized, not realized, not fulfilled.

Ethics, on the other hand, is a branch of philosophy that deals with moral issues. Ethics includes and encompasses the moral principles of a society, culture, person, group.

Morality is limited as a system of duty, obligation, principles of conduct, diligence.

On the other hand, morality contains a value system. This value system is a set of ethical values of a given person, organization, society, group, which represent a standard for human behavior in all situations - group, family, society.

For society, the actions of judges and prosecutors require their moral principles and ethical norms to correspond to the greater responsibility they fulfill, because they are an instrument of justice in society.

Four categories of value systems must be distinguished:

- Personal value system
- Spiritual value system public values

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- Career value system
- Family value system
- Cultural value system
- Social value system

Only some social value systems materialize in the form of legal codes and / or laws.

Therefore, even if a member of a group expresses and imposes a value that is in conflict with the value system of the group, certain bodies in the group may encourage or accordingly sanction this discrepancy. Our judiciary lacks such a system of control and sanction entirely. On the contrary, the system of control bodies such as the SJC and the SJC inspectorate actually stimulate non-compliance, violation, and disregard for the law by judges and prosecutors.

4. JUSTICE, ETHICS IN LAW from antiquity to modernity neoliberal capitalism ruled by the global Masonic mafia-driven elite and its deep rule and deep state

In the EGYPTIAN "Instructions for Pharaoh Mericure" around 2100 BC, it is written: The ruler must be just and support the weak.

In China, Confucius 551-479 BC. He says: that people should treat each other "as relatives" and follow the golden rule: "Do not do to others what you do not want to happen to you!"

Socrates 470-399 BC thinks the same way. According to Plato, justice is "the best thing to be loved by anyone who wants to be happy, both for himself and for the consequences for others."

Aristotle describes justice as the supreme virtue. He distinguishes between the two types of justice: distributive and compensatory.

He states: inequality is a source of discontent and ferment.

Justice according to Greek philosophers and "cardinal virtue".

Cicero 106-43 BC. He argues that justice should be understood as a principle of society.

The law is the principles and foundations of the philosophy of our existence.

Only in a legal society can there be a development of the creative, social, life, personal potential.

Every area of our lives is regulated by law.

Without law there can be no social life.

Zecons without morality are meaningless.

Moral and ethical norms and values are the laws above the cassocks of a society.

So it is important that morality, ethics in law does not disappear. Because if ethics and morality disappear, everything human disappears and there can be no society of people.

The law seeks to maintain a society in order, development, real existence, and the instinct that maintains a society and its life are legal. Justice is an ethical term. Only in Hammurabi's laws was morality combined in the laws.

In reality, values must be the main existing element of the laws.

Today, the lack of values and ethics, of moral and ethical values, in laws leads to chaos in the system, in laws, in law enforcement and among professional ethics among judges, prosecutors, lawyers, jurists.

The unethical behavior of lawyers, judges, prosecutors, lawyers, lawyers violates the dignity of the law. Judges, prosecutors must work for the truth to prevail because the truth is:

1 / . For the benefit of society as a whole and of all citizens

2 / . It would be wrong and fateful to replace truth with falsehood and deception.

When justice obeys the interests, the currency, then the essence of the law and the laws that make up the system is lost.

Law, moral principles - moral and ethical principles, justice, regulate the behavior of citizens in a society.

Ethical norms represent the minimum required bases and principles of law.

Justice today in the judiciary around the world is associated with interests and who will pay how much to get "justice" legally clothed in a court decision based on their personal interests clothed and paid for with money.

When the right, the law, the justice is violated, then there is chaos in a society, lack of justice, honesty, conscience, honor, dignity.

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Justice disputes Kant surpasses the phase of individual virtue and becomes the "formal principle of the possibility of legal status among people."

Marx dreams of a society in which the rule is valid: "Everyone according to his abilities, everyone according to his needs +.

However, if a system is mafiaized as a structure, functions, life, then this principle is only an empty system without content and essence.

Nietzsche 1844-1900 marked the beginning of skepticism, negativism, and moral criticism.

According to the American philosopher John Rawls 1921-2002, public wealth is created by all citizens and this is the reason why everyone should share it. - the "principle of differentiation".

According to Aristotle, the highest virtue is justice.

5. THEORY OF THE DEGREE OF JUSTICE / INJUSTICE - LAG OF JUSTICE in a neoliberal capitalist society created and governed by the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule

CRITICISM OF MODERN JUDICIAL SYSTEMS and

The justice / injustice relationship

Injustice on a global, national, religious, level.

When the degree of injustice reaches a critical point - a lag of injustice - the first lag, the country or people concerned, or the relevant decision of a judge is against the law and is evidence of mafia and corruption perish and disappear.

Corruption violates every law and does not bear any responsibility.

The degree of injustice is directly dependent on the degree of corruption.

Degradation of legal consciousness.

Non-compliance with the law becomes a legal and moral norm in a country. In the United States, for example, this was evidenced by judges' decisions on election irregularities in the United States 2020.

Moral degradation of judges, prosecutors is moral.

The norm is the criminal model of consciousness.

Vices become virtues, virtues the object of ridicule and mockery.

Demographic restructuring.

Growing inefficiency of social functions

the growth of impoverishment

DEGREE OF INJUSTICE - depends on the degree of MAFIOTISM in a society, the degree of corruption among law enforcement and law enforcement agencies, the degree of trust of civil society to all participants in government - court, prosecutor's office, how and whether judges and prosecutors obey the law, enforce the law, fail to enforce, break the law prosecutor's office, state, municipalities.

The DEGREE OF DEMOCRACIZATION OF A SOCIETY depends on the respective DEGREE OF UNJUSTICE / JUSTICE.

FAIR FORMULA / INJUSTICE:

JUSTICE / INJUSTICE = POWER + Influence + Relationships + Interests + MONEY / And + Mafia structure / internal or external / + Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - Obligation - Responsibility - morality ethics - observance / application / implementation of the law by judges / prosecutors / statesmen - Control / Sanctions - Corruption - Mafiatization - TRUST / DEGREE OF TRUST.

WHAT DEPENDS ON INJUSTICE / JUSTICE IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM:

DEGREE OF LEGALITY - LAWS ADOPTED

LEVEL OF APPLICATION OF LAWS

DEGREE OF DUALITY OF APPLICATION OF LAWS

DEGREE OF DUALITY OF LAWS ADOPTED

DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AND CONTRADICTION OF THE LAWS ADOPTED WITH THE BASIC LAW OF

DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS

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DEGREE OF EQUALITY
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF THE LAW BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LAW BY PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY GOVERNMENT, MINISTERS,
LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY MUNICIPAL / LOCAL AUTHORITIES
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS BY MINISTERS AND PRIME MINISTERS BY THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE ON THE EXECUTIVE POWER
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE FROM THE MAFIA IN ITS BENEFIT
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF MAFIA JUDGES
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF IMPUNITY OF CITIZENS
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS FROM THE EVIDENCE
LEVEL OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS - IMPACTED PRACTICE
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-COMPLIANCE OF DIRECTIVE ORDINANTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS
LEVEL OF NON-APPLICATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF VIOLATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF NON - COMPLIANCE WITH LAWS
LEVEL OF NON - APPLICATION OF LAWS
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE STATE APPARATUS
DEGREE OF MAFIONIZATION IN THE LOCAL MUNICIPAL APPARATUS
DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CONSTITUTION
LEVEL OF EXERCISE OF BASIC CIVIL RIGHTS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT GROUPS OF PEOPLE
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON RELIGIOUS BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON A CULTURAL BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT EDUCATIONAL LEVEL - CENSUS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION OF COMMUNITY NJVZH
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT BUSINESS LEVEL - MONOPOLY, OLIGOPOL AND OTHERS
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH JUDGES
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF CORRUPTION WITH STATES / MUNICIPAL
DEGREE OF THE MAFIA

There is a very rapid improvement in the financial situation of judges and prosecutors close to the government and the mafia. This only happens in three to four years. Judges and prosecutors buy homes with bank loans, just to cover up their extra income as judges - mostly unproven. The proof of the existence of corrupt practices and the receipt of bribes from judges is the fact that in just two or three years judges and prosecutors repay the loans taken by banking institutions for the purchase of their apartments. An analysis of income proves that it is practically impossible with their income as judges or prosecutors to pay their mortgages to banking institutions in just two or three years.

There is protection for judges at all levels in cases brought against Baku and financial institutions

There is protection of judges at all levels in cases filed against actions of persons from the Ministry of Interior, various state institutions

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There are courts that decide professionally on cases against the Council of Ministers, ministries, the National Revenue Agency and other institutions - the ADMINISTRATIVE COURTS.

Corrupt practices in the courts: deliberate distribution of judges in court cases.

Examples of high-level corruption - Vlahov, Deputy Chairman of the Supreme Court of Cassation, orders judges to hear cases without using the random distribution of cases.

POSTPONEMENT OF CASES

VIOLATION OF LAWS in court cases in favor of the MAFIA and persons and companies belonging to the mafia.

THE PRACTICE to issue insane acts in violation of any laws.

PRACTICE of judges belonging to the mafia is to issue such acts with such arguments and motives, completely insane, using the veiling of motives, meaningless philologization of legal norms, creation of PERSONAL CPC by judges - in violation of CPC.

AREAS OF DISTRIBUTION OF INJUSTICE

Injustice can be found in court, prosecutor's office, state, ministers, executive institutions, regulatory bodies, controlling bodies, bodies protecting and controlling the rights and freedoms of citizens, personal data, discrimination, executive services.

They depend on the mafiaization of a society, on practices, traditions, political and economic development, the specifics of a society, the socio-cultural environment, laws, morals, rules, norms, morals and ethics of behavior of citizens, judges, prosecutors, statesmen, employees and others.

Areas of manifestation of corruption are:

- 1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes government, government departments, and institutions, local governments, and others.
- 2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations. Adoption of laws that are unconstitutional and the basic law protecting rights.
- 3 /. The sphere of the judiciary / judges / prosecutors / investigators
- 4 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /
- 5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance and others.
- 6 /. The sphere of the private sector - business organizations, companies both local and international, global and transnational.
- 7 /. The field of media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /
- 8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

Justice / injustice is mostly characteristic of the public sector, but it is also found in the private sector.

Justice / injustice depends on the mafiaization of a society, on corruption and the degree of corruption in a society.

FORMS OF INJUSTICE / JUSTICE IN THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The forms of injustice / fairness in public administration are the following:

1. Failure to comply with a lawful request by a person entitled to do so by an employee of the relevant administration. Manifesting in open refusal, tacit refusal and others.
2. When the government or the respective administration, body, institution is a seller and does not fulfill the law, it violates the law, not applied by the law.
3. When the government or the respective administration, body, institution is a buyer or consumer of certain services and does not fulfill the law, it violates the law, does not apply the law.
4. When state and other institutions - municipal carry out right-wing transactions, and do not comply with the law, violate the law, do not apply the law.
5. When the executive power controls financial and credit institutions, companies with licenses, companies with concessions, permits and others, and does not comply with the law, violates the law, does not apply the law.
6. When the executive power distributes limited funds, subsidies, grants, investments, social payments and others and does not comply with the law, it violates the law, does not apply the law.
7. When there is a service for granting and permitting specific activities, permits, licenses and other regimes for carrying out a specific activity and does not comply with the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

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8. When collecting taxes, fees, customs duties - does not comply with the law, violates the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

9. When collecting fines, sanctions - does not comply with the law, violates the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

10. When state and other types of employees are authorized and authorized to perform control functions and to sanction third parties or companies in case of non-compliance and do not comply with the law, do not apply the law, violate the law, violate the law in favor of private interests.

11. When government or other types of employees have important inside information and do not comply with the law, do not apply the law, violate the law in someone's private interests

12. When there is non-transparency in decision-making and implementation of a decision or choice of decision.

JUSTICE / INJUSTICE IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

The monopoly on the judiciary and the maintenance of public order is the most important prerequisite for the generation of corrupt practices in the judiciary and the police.

An important factor is the inaccuracy, incompleteness, the presence of gaps in the relevant laws, regulations, procedures, deadlines, inconsistency of laws, inaccuracy of procedures, violation of procedures and deadlines in the judiciary, the feeling of impunity by magistrates, police, prosecutors, investigators.

Corruption in the judiciary and the police is the most important factor in the spread, imposition, growth of corruption in the entire public sector.

It generates a sense of impunity for corrupt officials, a sense of injustice among the oppressed, a sense of a double standard of law for different strata and groups of people.

THE SPECIFICITY OF JUSTICE / CORRUPTION IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

1. The monopoly of knowledge and skills.

2. Existence of omissions, inconsistencies between different laws.

3. Failure to comply with deadlines and procedures in court proceedings.

4. Personnel crisis in the judiciary. The promotion of junior judges, relatives of senior judges, prosecutors known to senior judges and prosecutors, etc.

5. Crisis in the objective appointment and promotion of judges, prosecutors, investigators. There is political influence here, as well as influence from the executive branch.

6. Simultaneous action of incompatible legal norms

7. Existence of a practical lack of responsibility and responsibility for poorly done work, for an illegal decision.

8. Lack of clear rules for assessing the professional qualities of employees.

9. Lack of professional traditions.

10. Lack of limitation of competencies.

Other areas of corruption - in politics, the economy and the public sector - will not be addressed in this report.

MANIFESTATIONS OF CORRUPTION ACTION LEADING TO INJUSTICE in judges, prosecutors, state / municipal officials

The following manifestations of corruption and behavior in judges, prosecutors, tax officials, police officers, civil servants are based on a study of over 137 cases and cases in these areas.

Manifestations before a judge: 1. interest, 2. incompetence, 3 alleged incompetence, 4 kinship bias, 5 official bias, 6 judicial solidarity, 7 inaction, 8 delayed action, 9 regional bias - bias towards a fellow citizen - the district, the city, 10 bias towards relatives by services, etc., 11 bribes, 12 court proceedings not according to establishments member, and on another or non-existing in the respective claim, 13 "nagging" - finding any non-existent reasons for delaying the case or leaving it without motion, 14 others.

Manifestations at the prosecutor's office: 1. interest, 2 incompetence, 3 bias, 4 imaginary incompetence, 5 family bias, 6 official bias, 7 prosecutorial solidarity, 8 bias towards fellow citizens, 9 bias towards relatives in the line of services and others, 10 bribes, 11 inaction, 12 others.

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Manifestation with state / municipal / tax officials: 1. inaction, 2 taking an alternative decision, 3 delaying the decision. 4 bribes, 5 issuance of inside information, 6 tenders, privatization, 7 others.

6 / .. THEORY OF THE MAFIA AND MAFIOTISM IN SUPPORT OF INJUSTICE IN A CAPITALISTIC SOCIETY

The differences between fascism and mafia are minimal. This will be explained in the text below.

State capitalism - is a system in which the state replaces private entrepreneurs in their role as factors - capitalists.

Under state capitalism, all property and all means of production are concentrated in the hands of one capitalist - the state, which in most cases is governed by the party elite and party nomenklatura.

The value added of production is redistributed by the sole capitalist, the state. It is often called either socialist or communist.

It is often argued that the countries of the socialist bloc are neither popular nor social, and that the economic system is in fact state capitalism.

Capitalism is an economic system in which production and trade are privately owned and governed by market economy methods, which in turn follow the principles of supply and demand. The main engine in such a system and supposedly "competition".

Fascism - professes the idea of a one-party state,. Fascism believes that nations and races are in constant conflict, Fascist governments forbid and suppress criticism and opposition to themselves.

They are opponents of class conflict.

Fascism is a state government similar to that of Mussolini, which elevates the nation and the race above the individual, establishes a one-party system, promotes nationalism, imposes strict economic and social control, applies violence, censorship

PRINCIPLES OF MAFIOTISMUS - THE NEW TYPE OF GOVERNMENT IN PRIVATE AND PERSONAL INTERESTS

The state is governed by the Prime Minister, if the same state is a parliamentary republic, which has set up and governs each state institution - ministry, state agency, manages both the executive and the judiciary through appointments close to him, and governs the legislature. power - the parliament.

The people are a mob according to mafia. Principles of crowd management: suppressing the masses to be guided by petty passions.

Creating problems of the "crowd" - the people through taxes, high prices, high interest rates on banking services, management of free funds of middle class citizens, thus through cunning and hypocrisy suppress the greatest human virtues - openness and honesty, which according to mafia are vices,

The rule of law - where the law begins, where it ends.

Exiled force of laws, "liberalized" rights ",The right of the strong, Intervenes and removes all existing regulations and decrees.

Mafiotismus puts its hand on the laws, reorganizes the institutions, what is necessary and useful is only for their goals and aspirations.

In this part we will consider the main elements, relationships of mafia theory, seen in the twenty years of experience in this field of the author. The following is the author's view of the creation of a mafia theory, its formation and consideration as a theory. Along with the main elements of the theory, specific manifestations of the mafia of specific types of employees are considered here. These manifestations have crystallized on the basis of a study by the author of over 137 cases in the judiciary, tax services, government institutions and others.

ELEMENTS OF THE MAFIA THEORY are the following:

1 /. STRUCTURE OF THE MAFIA. It includes any structures that obey the mafia formula.

2 /. STRUCTURAL SUBORDINATION. This is present both in an external structure, mostly described as an organized criminal group, and in an internal structure - this is about every structure of the state power, the executive power, the legislative power, the judiciary. This is subordination chief-subordinate. Here the hierarchy is strict and the duties are performed from top to bottom, impartiality.

3 /. FUNCTIONAL SUBJECTION. This type of subordination of members, employees and others is valid both for the internal structures - the structures of the state power, the executive power, the judiciary, and for the external structures - especially in mafia structures there is a subordination. In some groups in Bulgaria there are even ranks - private, corporal, lieutenant and others, which characterize the functional subordination of the members. .

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The structures of the mafia are: - External structure - of criminal groups, of economic groups, internal structure - state structure - executive power, judiciary.

4 /. CONNECTIONS. There are several types of connections between these structures that are part of Mafia: - Connections between internal and external structure, - Connections between internal structures, - Connections between external structures.

5 /. Existence of mafia action - the prerequisite is the presence of a COMMAND - ORDER. The order is executed on the basis of:

5. 1 /. subordination - structural or functional

5. 2 /. On mutually beneficial cooperation / external and internal ./

"You carry out my orders - I support you. You get a post, you get paid."

6 /. Types of mafias: - internal judicial mafia, internal prosecutorial mafia, state mafia, external judicial mafia, external prosecutorial mafia, external state mafia.

MAFIA FORMULA

The simplest model of the mafia, which describes the factors that affect the size, type and type of the mafia is the following:

MAFIA = Power + Influence + Relationships + Interests + ORDER / And + Mafia structure / internal or external structure / + Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - obligation - responsibility - morality / ethics .

The mafia is typical of both the public sector and the private sector. The mafia is characterized by the interaction of the private sector with the public sector. Interactions between different structures are based on connections and contacts on a close friendly or subordinate level of dependence in one structure, be it an external or internal structure of the mafia.

In the interaction between the two types of interests and representatives of the two sectors, especially in justice, there is an order, which is set by a member of the internal structure by him personally in his interest or by a member of the internal structure on the basis of an order from an external structure. for a selfish purpose.

AREAS OF MAFIA DISTRIBUTION

The mafia can be found in all spheres of public life.

Areas of manifestation of the mafia are: -1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes government, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, - 2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non - profit associations,. The sphere of the judicial system / judges /, - 4 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, - 5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc., - 6 /. The sphere of the private sector,. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, - 8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

The power of the mob in the service of mafia is blind, unreasonable, unreasonable, serving left and right.

Mafiotismus suggests freedom, equality, brotherhood, justice - pushing for debauchery, drunkenness. Cunning, hypocrisy, violence, robbery and terror.

Terror is carried out on all vertical and horizontal structures of the executive branch.

The terror is carried out in favor of the mafia and its representatives from the prosecutor's office, the judiciary.

The terror is carried out through the National Revenue Agency, the Ministry of Interior, the Prosecutor's Office, tax services, municipal services and others.

Mafiotismus dominates the most important factor of public thought - the press and print media, all types of media - especially television, the Internet.

The thought of the crowd moves through the press and the media. The role of the press and the media is to be: to sense the needs, to convey the complaints and to reveal the dissatisfaction of the people. The press proclaims free speech. But this is apparent. News events are managed and controlled by representatives of mafia.

Authority and political decay - abuse of power, understanding of the pursuit of independence

The impoverished people are in hopeless slavery, they have only fictitious rights.

The misery of life oppresses the masses. There are rights in the constitution that are really fictitious, not real. Which are violated in every way in all laws passed by the parliament.

Rights are real abducted ideas that never in practice

The famine and the degeneration of the masses

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With constant needs, constant costs, constant increases in costs, taxes, constant indebtedness - hunger, taxes, debts - give birth to a slavish dependence that rules the crowds, and their hands and minds are blocked for various other thoughts,

Liberalism

When the people realize that in the name of their freedom they make concessions and condescension, they realize that they are in power and attack the government. The people are like a blind man who encounters all kinds of obstacles, problems, helplessly looking for a protector - a support that he does not find when he does not remember to return to his first position - obediently puts his rights in power.

Speculation is a major form of business and business relationships.

It is capital that drives the world, and it drives slavery that rules industry and trade

Weakened public opinion. - those who think and oppose, must learn to think, mental forces must be directed in a verbal skirmish of legal time and eloquence.

Societies must be deceived and lied to and manipulated

Chaos in public thought. The civil society is replaced and replaced by the NGOs financed by the mafia and the replacement of the civil society is practically realized and carried out.

To lose in proverbs no opinion on political issues, and political issues these issues are not within their competence of society, but only of the one who leads the game.

Another strategy - the people's shortcomings, habits, passions, rules of relationships to swear so much that to create chaos from which there is no way out.

People stop understanding each other and they don't need to deny the people to think about political issues and change their solution.

Personal initiatives must also be confronted - against each other in order to become meaningless.

Monopolies destroy wealth.

Capital humiliates agriculture.

Increase in wages and at the same time increase in prices. The increase in wages is not in favor of workers, because at the same time prices will be increased, the rise in prices of basic necessities at times due to the increase in wages.

The representatives of mafia hold the social forces. They are legislators, they determine the composition of the court and they administer justice, they punish, they pardon, they judge

They hold all these positions in their hands

Mafiotismus holds in its hands the unbridled ambitious, insatiable, greedy, ruthless of revenge, the vicious, the hated, the envious.

Mafiotismus deploys state institutions, education, upbringing, municipal structures and all kinds of government, creates disorderly arbitrariness, affects the rule of law, with liberal disorderly arbitrariness.

Deliberately complicate and confuse the legislation.

Judges do not comply with the law, no one can punish them, no one wants to punish judges, there is no institution to punish them, to sanction them, to dismiss them.

Mafiotismus and its representatives at the state level create support and support the PROCESS OF GOD'S CHOSEN IN COURT AND PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE. Judicial acts are issued that distort interpretations, contradict the law and its proper implementation, create case law in a judicial system that does not allow such a right, create case law that grossly violates the laws and rights of individuals and companies, issue conflicting interpretations.

Mafiotismus and its representatives affect the judiciary, election institutions, the press, the media, individual freedom, education and upbringing as cornerstones of free life.

The institutions are fragmented and divided among themselves the power of the state - legislative, executive and judicial power. If one part is damaged, the whole country and its actions are damaged. The state has suffered from a lack of justice, a lack of enforcement by judges, and a lack of enforcement by prosecutors.

In reality, the blood of the state is poisoned - when the judiciary is poisoned. Then this country is best run by mobsters.

"The mafia appoints and appoints judges and prosecutors. The three pillars of chaos are completely dependent on mafia.

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Mafia control and control of corruption in the judiciary - court and prosecutor's office, administration, ministries. People are appointed who have something dark in the past, a mistake in their lives, violations of the law, there is an affair, there is a crime. Such persons are faithful and do all the things they are told to carry out orders, orders, for fear of being exposed. They seek to preserve the privileges, the power, the benefits, the respect, the power, the power, the rights to do what they want without being punished.

Destroying in the constitutions everything that hinders the mafia and passing in them what seizes the own content of the constitutions and the rights of the citizens.

Anti-corruption institutions are being set up, which are set up by representatives of mafia, but do not actually enforce the laws, but cover up the crimes of their members and servants,

Exhaustion of the population and citizens in their own daily problems of survival.

Disenfranchisement of the population. Real deprivation of the rights and freedoms of citizens demonstrated in the constitutions and their replacement in another by-laws in lawlessness.

Real destruction of the freedoms of the citizens in the other laws and the real depersonalization of the rights and freedoms of the citizens in the constitution.

This leads to the seizure of all rights, it is done so that the laws will prohibit and allow only that, which is in the interest of the mafia and their personal interest.

The entire press and all media are closely controlled by mafia people.

Persons with a different opinion will not be allowed to go to the media, television, radio, newspapers, magazines,.

PUBLIC RESOURCE CONTROL SYSTEM

Literature and journalism are the two most important educational forces. The mafia will become the owner of almost 100 percent of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines, which control about 90-95 percent of the population.

COMPROMISE SYSTEM.

In this way and with these methods, judges and prosecutors, statesmen, officials, ministers,
Through compromising and

SYSTEM OF LAWS

Through audit acts of revenue and other state agencies, tax offices, which prove violations, obligations of persons and companies in especially large amounts, will be kept companies and persons in subordination, not presenting these documents, and they will be kept in logs. ready at any time to be activated and used against the person or company.

REAL ESTABLISHMENT OF AN IMAGINARY OPPOSITION

Which will carry out apparent attacks and protests In reality, the shootings at political and any level will be in vain and imaginary.

COVERAGE AND LEGALIZATION OF PERFORMANCE BY THE MAFIA IN THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE

In order for the mafia to work in the prosecutor's office, the top of this organization should be a person to serve the mafia.

DISTRACTION FROM IMPORTANT POLICY ISSUES

DETERMINING PUBLIC ATTENTION FROM SERIOUS ISSUES.

KILLING THE LAWS, THE PRESTIGE OF THE POWER OF THE LAW.

- Failure to comply with the law.
- Breaking the law to the detriment of competitors, enemies of the mafia.
- Legalization of crimes committed by prime ministers, ministers, people of the mafia.
- Free interpretation of laws.
- The free implementation of the laws depending on the client, the people and the companies of the mafia.

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- Resolving lawsuits in favor of the mafia and people mafia in complete violation of laws and principles of law.

CREATION OF LAWS THAT WILL LEGALIZE REPRESSION AND LAWLESSNESS AND RACKETS AND EXTRACTION OF COMPANIES BY THE MAFIA - THE GOVERNMENT.

EXECUTION OF MAFIA ORDERS IN ALL COURTS.

THE ADMINISTRATIVE COURTS WILL LEGALIZE THE CRIMES OF THE EXECUTIVE, THE GOVERNMENT, THE MINISTERS, THE PRIME MINISTER.

THE ADMINISTRATIVE COURTS WILL TERMINATE THE CASES AGAINST STATE INSTITUTIONS, MINISTRIES, MINISTERS, MINISTERS-PRESIDENTS, - EXECUTIVE.

APPOINTMENT OF JUDGES AND PROSECUTORS IN FAVOR OF THE MAFIA.

ESTABLISHMENT OF INSTITUTIONS THAT WILL COVER UP CRIMES, VIOLATIONS OF LAWS BY JUDGES AND PROSECUTORS

Judges carry out only orders of the mafia, honest citizens and companies to lose cases.

The extortion of judges takes place only on the basis of the execution of mafia orders.

Election of judges and prosecutors only after the acceptance of orders, exclusion of an agreement that they will execute orders of the mafia.

The application of the law by judges and prosecutors will follow the principle of the mafia's order, not the application of the law.

Judges and prosecutors are appointed only if they belong to the mafia.

Establish institutions and inspectors that will not punish lawlessness and crimes committed by mafia courts and prosecutors.

The fear of not being promoted, not being promoted to the rank of judge or prosecutors.

Creating conditions for raising and raising judges, police officers and prosecutors in rank - the only execution of mafia orders.

DESTRUCTION OF FEAR AND DEATH IN COURT, PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

CREATION OF FEAR AND UNBEARABLE OBEDIENCE TO ALL AND EVERYTHING ONLY IN FAVOR OF THE MAFIA.

ABSOLUTISM AS A PRINCIPLE OF POWER

REMOVAL OF THE LAW OF CASSATION

In the Bulgarian art. 280 of the Civil Procedure Code -

Inclusion of the right of cassation in the power of the ruler and the mafia

The press will fall under strict censorship of the mafia only in its favor.

Real use of all media tools and the press for the benefit and interests of the mafia.

Different treatment of laws by judges and prosecutors.

Criminal cases against people belonging to the mafia will be decided in their favor in violation of any legal provisions.

Criminal cases against people who oppose the government's mafia will be resolved in violation of the laws to their detriment and their destruction - both intellectually, physically, mentally.

A halo of government infallibility and "non-violation" of the laws will be built.

A system of infallibility of laws will be created by the government despite their widespread violation.

Violation of the law, the rights and freedoms of citizens by the government, ministers, state institutions, will go unpunished by both the court and the prosecutor's office.

Appointment of the Prosecutor General and prosecutors by members of the mafia and the government - personally by the Prime Minister, ..

In this way it will be ensured that for any violation, violation of the laws, commission of crimes under the Criminal Code will not be punished by a court and prosecutor's office.

The guilty members of the mafia will be acquitted.

For the same cases, opponents of the mafia will be punished in violation of any laws.

The ultimate goal is to ruin human lives, businesses, entire families.

The goal will be theft and misappropriation of businesses, real estate, mafia competitors.

State agencies will comply with the regulations - even verbally of the Prime Minister and his ministers in violation of any law.

Centralized GOVERNANCE of the state - by the mafia, starting with the Prime Minister.

Centralized management and control of ministers by the Prime Minister. Control of the actions and decisions of the ministers by employees of the Prime Minister.

Control and management of all public procurement, appointed by one ministry, by people of the mafia and the Prime Minister. Control and management of all public procurements to be won by companies close to the mafia, respectively by the Prime Minister and his ministers.

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Preparation of the conditions of each public procurement to be satisfied as mandatory conditions only by a mafia company and a company close to the Prime Minister and his ministers.

Creation of a mechanism for renegotiation of the conditions of the won public procurement by a mafia company, the aim being to raise the price of the public procurement indefinitely.

Creating a mechanism of only winning the public procurement by a company close to the mafia and raising the price indefinitely.

The people are a crowd and we need to create a system, to become more stupid to have more problems with administration, management - tax, real estate, indebtedness, not to look at the problems of society and. The problems - HIGH LOANS, High interest rates, expensive food, expensive value of services.

RULES OF THE MAFIA FOR GOVERNMENT government services, institutions, civil servants, judges and prosecutors and others.

7 /. Principles of the Global Masonic Mafia-driven Elite and its DEEP GOVERNANCE AND DEEP STATE ruled by it - short description, concept, content

The global Masonic mafia elite and its deep government and deep state is a corporate, militarized, functionally defined, mafia group of people who run and own financial, banking, corporate, IT companies, not elected by the citizens of the countries that actually run not only a specific country, but also a group of countries, on the principles of Mafia and financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism.

The global Masonic mafia elite and its deep government and deep state have corrupted and mafiotized all spheres of society on which the government of a country, of a union depends - in the case of the European Commission and the European Union, the United States and other countries where they rule. people of the deep state.

All members of the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state are Freemasons and belong to different secret societies, regardless of which. For years, all secret societies have been occupied from within by the representatives and bearers of the goals and aspirations of the Illuminati for a new world genocide and dictatorship over humanity. For these Freemasons the oath is to obey the law of the lodge and not to comply with any other laws - those of states, international law, unions and others and to do everything in the name and for the benefit of the lodge, observing only the laws of the lodge, but not to the state concerned, to international law, even to commit crimes, to help members of the lodge when they are in trouble, and to carry out the plan of the lodge. All laws and rules are subject to a vow of ideology and faith in Lucifer and the church of Lucifer / Satan.

And the plan is one - to conquer the world, to rule the world by one world government, only by them - the global Masonic mafia elite.

Concept - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

The global Masonic mafia elite and ruled by it DEEP GOVERNMENT AND DEEP GOVERNMENT is an organization, structure, government, kleptocracy, and cryptocracy of a group of people from the financial banking, resource, technology, corporate elite that GLOBALANCIAL MALIFALISM countries of the principles of Mafiorism and of the financial bank resource technological mafiotized Materialism.

AREAS OF GOVERNANCE, CONTROL, THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE MANAGED BY IT, THE MAFIA IN MAFIOTISM

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state can be found in all spheres of public life, in all states, governments.

The spheres of action, goals, tasks, management, control, manifestation of global Yamason mafia elite and the deep state ruled by it and the global Masonic mafia elite through mafia and on the basis of financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism through the mafia are as follows:

1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes governments, prime ministers, ministers, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, their control through compromising and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations, the degradation of the political elite, their control through compromising, and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

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3 /. Control and management of national security systems, secret services, intelligence services. Control and management of the management and administration of intelligence services, intelligence agencies, departments of internal security, intelligence services - space, central security services, national security services, intelligence and counterintelligence

4 /. Control and management of the sphere of military structures, defense structures, defense structures, military-industrial complex

5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc.,

6 /. The sphere of the private sector, companies, corporations,

7 /. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, their control and management through racketeering, coercion, pressure, sanctions and others.

8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

9 /. Banking and financial sector

10 /. Social networks and information technologies

11 /. The sphere of the judicial system / judges, prosecutors, investigators /, their control through addictions - bribes, gifts, excursions, knotrol through compromising, and other addictions - sexual, gambling and others.

12 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, their control through addictions, bribes, and others.

13 /. Control and management and conquest is the indebtedness of a country through the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the European Central Bank, the International Bank for Settlements and other world banks.

14 /. Control and management of monopoly companies, controlling and having monopoly influence all over the world through investment companies, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite - BlackRock and other companies.

15 /. Directions and management of state treasury intelligence,

16. The overthrow of regimes through "yellow", "orange" revolutions and the appointment of governments, presidents to serve the interests of the deep state

17 /. Provoking occasions for starting and starting wars against countries whose territories with the respective natural resources are of interest to the representatives of the deep state.

18 /. Imposition of policy in the respective countries, which are of the economic interests of the deep state and their profits from it.

19 /. Imposition of a policy in the case of NATO for the purpose of threats, wars against third countries from the territories of foreign countries.

20 /. Imposing a world government A new world order that will allow them to more easily govern countries, nations, peoples, economies, industries, finance, capital.

21 /. Creating conditions, causing chaos through various schemes and occasions - wars, refugee waves, crises - social, social, political, economic, state schemes with the ultimate goal of profits - economic, financial - profit and personal gain.

22 / - Management, control, manipulation, zombies of the civil society, through non-governmental organizations, their financing / example SOROS /,

23 /. Imposing their requirements for military budgets of all countries in order to sell weapons from their companies in the military-industrial complex to countries, countries. 21 /. Control of criminal groups and groups

24 /. Control of trade, military, criminal groups, the defense industry, the financial sector, corporate media and counterterrorism.

25 /. Managing the military budgets of states, at least more than half goes to military spending and the purchase of equipment and weapons.

26 /. Control and management of the military-industrial complex

27 / Control and management of the state money, budgets, of the respective state

28 /. Management of many non-governmental national and international structures - the Council on Foreign Relations, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Trust Commission, the Bilderberg Group, the Club of Rome, the Committee of 300,

29 /. Supranational governance of the countries of the planet.

30 /. Management of International Institutions - UN, UNICEF, World Health Organization,

31 /. Committing crimes against people, individuals, services

32 /. Imposing globalization as an ideology

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33 /. Imposing the ideology and society of lesbianism, gay, bisexual and transgender people - LGBT people as a leader at the state level.

34 /. Use of compromising control of individuals - politicians and any others on whom depends the state and other decisions responsible for society as a whole.

35 /. Create a program, plan, and accomplish the task of destroying Christianity.

36 / Destruction of the family as a basic building block of society.

37 /. Targeted organization of migration through refugee waves, crises

38 /. Control and management of the election process in each country, imposing organization, management of the election process through various schemes of falsification and fraud.

39 /. Social terrorism of society from a moral, spiritual, economic point of view.

40 /. Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, facial recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, searching for information on the network, health card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded mobile applications, used applications, traffic, online transactions, text messages sent, and messages

41 /. Terrorist actions through the US and NATO and other military organizations

42 /. Terrorist actions through private formations

43 /. Ruin and collapse of the education system

44 /. killing the national achievements of democracy

45 /. destruction of the social system

46 /. polarization of society

47 /. destruction of national values

48 /. destruction of the national culture

49 /. destruction of rights and freedoms

50 /. destruction of the middle class

51 /. increasing poverty and inequality

52 /. increase begging

53 /. Indebtedness of countries, governments through the IMF, WB, ECB

54 /. Dependence of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines,

55 /. Control, management of the drug business since the 18th century by the black aristocracy

56 /. Creating inequalities in society, managing these inequalities, destroying the middle class, with the ultimate goal of enslaving society.

57 /. Creating conditions for control and management of the economies of entire countries with the sole purpose of personal gain.

58 /. Creation of a university elite - a Masonic mafia-dominated global elite to rule states, and other institutions in favor of the Global Masonic elite.

59 /. Control and management of education in a country in order to blunt, greater control and management of the masses and the younger generation in order to zombie and manage and control at any level - emotional, educational, social and others.

60 /. Creating a system for SOCIAL GEOCITE

61 /. Control is the management of health care with the ultimate goal of reducing the population of the planet,

62 /. Control and management of the system of drug development and dependence of the population on drugs.

63 /. Control and management of patents and developments and elimination of scientists who created discoveries that can improve people's lives.

64 /. Control and liquidate scientists, creators of drugs, but new methods of treatment that are cheap and hinder the wealth of the elite.

65 /. Control and liquidation of scientists creating systems for zero-point generators and free energy generators.

66 /. Control, management, drug production and addiction among the population with the ultimate goal of profit.

67. Control, creation of GMO products, food, for the purpose of profit and reduction of the population.

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68 /. Population control and management through food, lethal medicine, lethal vaccines, psychiatric medicines, deadly food, deadly grain, deadly sweeteners, GMOs, deadly water, air,

69 /. Control and management of the media, conquest of the media, and propaganda only of their goals, ideas, aspirations, plans, disguised under the slogan that care for humanity and the people in it.

70 /. Establish institutions that will govern countries, policies, such as the UNO, UNICEF and others

71 /. Control of the special and secret services through their Freemasons to serve their lodges and personal interests, but not the laws of the respective state.

72 /. Establishment of their own structures, in which their people will be members who will later govern and lead states - Council on Foreign Relations, 1921 and branches - Institute for Pacific Relations - New York, Center for Foreign Policy Studies - Paris, Institute for foreign policy - Hamburg, Royal Institute of International Affairs -1920, Bilberberg Group - 1954, Club of Rome - 1968, Trilateral Commission 1973, to determine the international policies of states, to govern states.

73 /. Creation of an elite by the University of Global Masonic Mafia Elite - Yale University, Harvard, Columbia, Corel University, New York University, Sarah Lawrence's University, Stanford University, University of Chicago, John Copkins, Brown University,

74 /. Control and management of all Masonic lodges - Knights Templar, Freemasonry, Rosicrucians, lodge of Gnosticism, Kabbalism, the Illuminati Freemasons through the principles of the Church of Lucifer.

75 /. Control and management of the elite and societies and states through Foundations - Rockefeller Foundation, Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowment, Clinton Foundation,

76 /. Media management and control, proprietary television - BBC, CBC, CNN, CBS, ABC, CNN and others, telegraph agencies - the Associated Press, Reuters and others, newspapers - New York Times, Washington Post, Wall Street Journal, Boston Globe, Baltimore Sun, Chicago Sun Times, Los Angeles Stays, Houston Post, Minneapolis Star / Tribune and others,

magazines. Fortune, Time, Life, Money, People, Newsweek, Business Week, Readers Ridge, US EU News and World Report, and others, dozens of publishers,

77 /. Propaganda and manipulation to reduce critical thinking

-- increasing the closedness, depression, dependence, feelings of slavery and dependence on the decisions and actions of the government

-- turning one's back on the real facts and evidence

-- dependence on propaganda

-- dependence on the promoted fear and stress

-- increase in mental illness

-- increase in drug abuse

-- increase in the number of homeless people

-- increase in the unemployed

-- increase in malnourished people

-- increase in malignant incurable diseases

-- increase in theft

-- increase in crime

-- increase in homicides

-- increasing the bankruptcies of companies

- reducing the duration of

78 /. Control by the global Yamason mafia elite of each state and its management through the control and management of the special services and secret services of the respective state.

79 /. Control by the global Masonic mafia elite of all Masonic and other and all kinds of Masonic lodges around the world.

80 /. Control and management of the election, election and appointment of presidents, prime ministers, chancellors in the respective countries from the structures of the deep state.

81 /. Falsifying the elections in order to win the elections of this party, which is under the rule of the global Masonic and mafia elite and the deep government and the deep state. Managing the process of election fraud in countries where the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state rule.

82 /. The global Masonic mafia elite rules, controls the deep state in every country on the planet.

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The deep government and the deep state and its representatives act as a shadow government. The deep state does not respect the rights, freedoms, constitutions of the respective state, the treaties for the formation of alliances, such as the European Union

In reality, Deep Governance and Deep State use the following undemocratic models of governance as follows:

- Autocracy
- Oligarchy
- Plutocracy
- Kleptocracy
- Corporatocracy
- Cryptocracy

All these systems of government are managed on the basis of the principles of MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism.

8 /. THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY IN THE SOCIETY OF THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM by Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev

The theory of socio-humanism was developed by Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova in the distant 2006. after a full analysis of the shortcomings of modern democratic systems based on global neoliberal capitalism., of MAFIOTISM in modern countries, based on the principles of the global Masonic mafia elite, which governs entire countries, USA, EUROPE, highly developed countries such as Germany, Great Britain, and dozens of other countries on the principles of Financial-banking resource technological mafia Materialism with the ultimate goal gains huge profits from everything from creating crises and others.

THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM places man and his environment - ecological environment in the center of attention of this system with the ultimate goal of better, fairer governance of states and all paid, on the principles of direct democracy and different from the system of global and neoliberal capitalism - an economic system.

Economic management in the theory of socio-humanism is a different system, which is not aimed at profits, crises, making huge profits at the expense of the real practical existence of civilization.

THE ONLY APPLICATION OF THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM can guarantee the survival of the planet EARTH and its entire population, excluding the real actions of the Global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule and deep state.

DIRECT DEMOCRACY IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN A SOCIETY MANAGED ACCORDING TO THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM

The current system of government is not a democracy at all, as it is not a real democracy, but rather an aristocratic mafia oligarchy of the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule in the deep state.

The mechanism underlying this sham democracy is elections. Elections are elected on the basis of citizens' votes.

These representatives, in turn, elect their proxies and representatives in the executive branch.

History proves that these representatives are an elite that is mafia-like, corrupt, that looks only at its own interests and, if it enters the relevant parliament, forgets about its promises and goals and carries out activities that only bring it millions of profits.

le this elite becomes an aristocratic oligarchy that actually represents and ultimately defends the interests of themselves and of the few who give money and bribes, lobby with money and funds, property and more.

In the current "democracies", an election procedure by voting has been adopted and chosen.

In reality, companies and banks finance both countries in one election - for example, in the United States and the two candidates of the two major parties, and whoever wins after that will work for them again.

The current systems cannot be democracies because of the electoral systems and the established system of the global Masonic mafia elite to falsify elections.

With the establishment of this type of government in the late 18th century in Britain, then in the United States, and in France after 1789. its creators knew it had nothing to do with democracy.

They had no real intention of creating democracy.

All these systems were created by a Masonic mafia elite and the deep government and deep state ruled by it.

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For this Masonic mafia elite, the creation of democracy was really the creation of anarchy, and the rule of the common people.

Thus, they create government through representation, which has nothing to do with democracy.

They really wanted to end the rule of the aristocracy and replace it with their mafia-style system of government in which they would rule, to draw on the public good.

In reality, democracy is translated as "democracy", and that state power comes from the people for the benefit of the people and is divided into:

- Consensus democracy
- Referendum direct democracy
- Representative democracy through elected representatives

By people is meant the citizens.

Essential characteristics of democracy are equality, justice, brotherhood, freedom.

Equality of all citizens before the law and equal access to power.

The freedom of citizens is ensured through established rights and freedoms in relevant laws.

In a representative democracy, all votes have equal weight, but in reality the ability of citizens to become representatives is limited, their ability to come to power is limited.

In reality, however, there is no real political equality in the current systems.

Equality in representative government is only fictitious, formal, imaginary.

The elect in question are and represent an elite, nobles, of the upper class, not workers.

It was clear to the founders of democracy that no one would be overthrown by voting, and that the poor would never take power by voting in elections.

Just because elections are a form of falsification of free choice.

That is why it is convenient for all this global Masonic mafia elite to call this "democracy", which, however, has nothing to do with democracy.

A caste of politicians is being created.

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF DEMOCRACY ARE - EQUALITY AS POLITICAL EQUALITY:

The main element that shows the existence of a DEMOCRACY is the TRUE POLITICAL EQUALITY OF THE CITIZENS, which does not really exist at the moment.

Not social, economic, physical, cultural, ethnic, etc. and POLITICAL EQUALITY - EQUALITY IN THE POLITICAL DECISION-MAKING PROCESS.

In reality, decisions in a true democracy must be made collectively, through a general assembly of the people, and not through its elected representatives.

The Assembly is such a form of general assembly of citizens.

The misuse of the word democracy really makes it unworthy.

In reality, power is corrupted by this elite, because its value system is not the one guided by morality, honor, dignity, conscience.

The current type of social system, social system, economic system constantly causes crises in every sphere of human activity.

The constantly created and deliberately caused crises in international relations, politics, economics, education, healthcare are rooted in the main forms of the market economy - personal interest and the desire for ever-increasing profits.

There is a system of organization and management of people's lives from the outside, and they cannot have any control and influence over those who govern their lives. This system is full of contradictions that provoke crises that are actually caused by the global Masonic mafia elite and its led and run deep government and deep state. People's opinion is ignored, not taken into account, people's interests are violated, public goods are looted, and go to the management of private interests, under the pretext that man can not manage well state-owned companies, property, goods.

On the other hand, egoism, egocentrism, the pursuit of success at any cost and success that brings only profits, income, money, come to the fore, ignoring the development of human creativity.

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Only such behavior and value system is tolerated, which leads to profits for certain individuals, companies, for certain interests, political elite, global Masonic mafia elite.

It turns out that a system of government with a high vertical structure and a hierarchical pyramidal system of government increasingly ignores the interests of society and people, deletes them, replaces them with their own personal interests for profit.

On the other hand, the creative abilities of the person are suppressed, which does not necessarily bring profit, money, dividends and others.

Such abilities are rejected, ignored,

Apart from the fact that the hierarchical system of government, the vertical structure ceases to serve society and the people, at one point it uses all kinds of coercive forms and measures against the people themselves.

"The forms of 'democracy' that we have known so far, and which are based on the election of representatives to elect their representatives in power and in vertical hierarchical structures and organizations, have nothing to do not only with direct democracy but also with democracy.

Elected representatives elect their representatives, and in fact both control and accountability are lost

This is minime democracy.

An alternative to the current democracy is direct democracy. They build institutions that ensure that every member of society can be directly involved in decision-making at political, economic, social, environmental, cultural and all levels.

Capitalism generates a consumer society whose value system is quite low, whose value system satisfies only the lowest human needs of Maslow's pyramid, where the most important are the ego, money, profit in money.

The direct democracy and the society of THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova puts man and the whole system in which man lives environment, ecological environment - planet, plant animals in the center of this system.

The impact of these decisions on both the social system and the ecological system of the planet is always considered in decision-making.

In addition, the system of direct democracy of SOCIO-HUMANISM imposes on the one hand referendums on the choice of:

- Program plan for a specific period. These plans-programs concern - public life, economy, social system, healthcare, education, internal and external security, external political and economic and international relations, the system of innovations, system of creation of state and / or state / private partnerships

Need to change laws, create new laws

- Budgets for the implementation of these plans - programs for a specific period, which are controlled at periods by selected councils on a rotating basis.

- Rotational principle of qualified personnel to implement and implement these plan-programs, as these qualified personnel have precisely defined for this position capacity, knowledge, experience, experience, achievements and others. As the choice of these shots is for a specific time. For this period of time these shots

SHORT AND NON-RENEWABLE TERMS - Powers should be given for a short period. One-time and short terms.

EQUALITY - HUMAN, SOCIAL, SOCIAL IS THE CORE OF DEMOCRACY AND ITS SINGLE CONDITION.

As power corrupts, i.e. those in office will not have the opportunity to corrupt themselves.

CONTROL of the implementation of these adopted plan programs in each area

The control is from every citizen, constant access to the information about the plan-programs, their implementation

CONTROL - before the term, during the term, at the end of the term, after the term

CONTINUOUS ACCOUNTING

SANCTIONS - recall,

WITHDRAWAL CONTROL LEVERS.

INSTITUTIONS OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY

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The institutions are organized on a non-hierarchical basis.

The political, economic, social, ecological system are organized on the principle of self-government, control by citizens, accountability to citizens at any time, appropriate system of acceptance of these actions, sanction of actions that do not lead to the respective results, responsiveness of management .

THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

Election of the Prosecutor General, city, district prosecutors on the basis of referendums after meeting the relevant criteria and proposing the relevant plan-programs

Control, accountability, responsiveness

INSTITUTIONS OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY

All systems are organized on a system of self-government, and control by civil society accountability to civil society of the period, the corresponding system of sanctions and recall.

- On non-hierarchy
- Direct democracy is applied in every sphere of the public, political, economic, ecological, social, cultural life of the citizens.
- Equality of rights - political equality.

An additional institution of political equality is the RIGHT TO FREE SPEECH €

Real right but free speech enables every citizen to be a guardian of the public good, the public domain
ie THE RIGHT TO TAKE THE WORD AND THE RIGHT TO SPEAK and A BASIC PRINCIPLE in direct democracy.

EVERYONE HAS THE RIGHT TO TAKE THE WORD AT ANY TIME, ANY QUESTION.

Everyone can talk.

Purity of democracy

It is also the right to tell the truth, to expose the lie, without any consequences for the perpetrator.

This is the category - it makes citizens active, responsible for what they say, say. As well as the fact that these opinions expressed and others are important for the relevant institutions.

This helps citizens to be active in the whole process.

The possibility for citizens to be passive, whether out of fear, threats, or other racketeering, coercion, to tell the truth, must be destroyed.

Capitalism is the exact opposite and opposite of democracy.

Under capitalism, there is a concentration of capital, human and natural resources in the hands of a small group of people, the so-called global Masonic mafia elite.

Real democracy is that which belongs and serves the market of the owners of huge capital, finances and others - the global Masonic mafia elite - including Rothschild Rockefeller, Morgan, Soros, Bull Gates and families of the black aristocracy and 13 families ruling the world.

The capitalist system rests and survives only on this concentration of wealth, money and power.

All their companies have the power to do business that brings huge profits to it.

The lack of democracy also leads to the environmental problems and ecological crisis created by this global Masonic mafia elite.

Ie in SOCIO-HUMANISM the main task is to cover the interests of man, of the ecological system, in all its inhabitants,
ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS TO CLIMATE CRISIS AND SOLUTIONS require democracy.

9 / . DIRECT DEMOCRACY IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

INSTITUTIONS OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM BASED ON THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM by Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova

9.1 / . SYSTEM OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY AND CONTROL OF THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM based on the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova

We have unequivocally proven mafiaism and corruption in the judiciary around the world. The oligarchy and the global Masonic mafia elite rule not only the states, their government, finances, capital, create all kinds of crises, we will not list them, but also the judiciary.

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By mafiotizing the judiciary, this global mafiaized Masonic elite legalizes theft of assets, capital, companies, repression, racketeering, theft, legalizing crimes committed by them.

The system of direct democracy and control of the judiciary in the Society created on the basis of the Theory of SOCIO-HUMANISM is the following:

1 /. With precise, clear criteria for experience, practice, experience, evaluations, specializations when applying, junior judges are selected by respectively established citizens' councils on a rotating basis for a period of 2 / two / years, and the age cannot and should not be less for 30 years. To hold experience in law and legal sciences not less than 5-7 years. This is the election of junior judges at the district court level

2 /. The Citizens' Council exercises constant control during this two-year period of court cases, acts, in connection with precisely defined ethical and moral and professional rules of conduct of junior judges. In case of violation - sanction - system of sanctions.

3 /. Citizens' councils are elected on a rotating basis by professional lawyers for a term of one year.

4 /. City, district judges are elected by referendum, based on a program presented to the respective candidate, who meets specific conditions - professional, experience, experience, and others. These judges are elected for a term of 2 / two / years. They have no immunity. Control of the actions by a civil commission elected on a rotating basis for 1 / one / year.

5 /. The heads of all courts are elected in referendums by the civil society from the respective district - city, district, upon defense and presentation of a respective program by the candidate. Control of the actions of the respective head by a civil commission.

6 /. The heads of the supreme courts are elected by referendums from the entire population.

The heads of the courts of appeal shall be elected by referendum in the district concerned.

7 /. The Prosecutor General is elected by the entire population in a referendum, after presenting a program.

Control is carried out by the relevant civil law council, which is on a rotating basis for one year, and its members deal only with this at all times, have no right to advocate, provide services, consultations and more.

Prosecutors at the appropriate levels are elected on the same principles above.

9.2./ SYSTEM OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY AND CONTROL OF THE LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM based on the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova

1 /. Council on the agenda of changes to old laws, creation of new laws,

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis for 2-3 years full time, on salary, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice and others.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

This council has and performs the role of setting the agenda, choosing areas, areas for legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

2 /. Advice on areas of law - relevant type of law - example - administrative, criminal, civil law, property law, and others.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis for 2-3 years full time, on salary, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice and others.

This is a body of 15 to 20 people selected by lot.

This council makes proposals for changing old laws, for drafting new laws depending on areas of legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

3 /. Advice on proposals for amendments to laws, for the creation of new laws, which include relevant experts, non-governmental organizations, for the coordination of relevant laws in connection with the laws, preparation of final proposals for laws, paragraphs, articles of laws.

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System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies. There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates. In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis for 2-3 years full time, on salary, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice and others. This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people. This council has and implements and makes proposals for changes in laws, creation of new laws, change of existing laws.

4 /. COUNCIL - jury for voting on the relevant laws.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis for 2-3 years, being called to vote on the relevant laws for one week a month, receiving additional remuneration.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

5 /. Council for control of the legislative process, control of application of laws, implementation of laws, consideration of complaints and others.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies. There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates. In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis for 2-3 years full time, on salary, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice and others. This is a body of 15 to 20 people selected by lot. This council has and performs the role of control of the legislation, control for monitoring the implementation of laws, the application of laws by judges.

CONCLUSIONS

In this article we show the system of control, direct democracy in the judiciary and lawmaking in a country.

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